

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.20 0.25 0.30 0.35

55°36'00"

09

$z_{\text{Sp}} = 0.81512$

35'40"

20"

00"

Dec (J2000)

16^h07^m30^s28^s

26^s

24^s

22^s

RA (J2000)

H
30 kpc